

Educational Mobility as a Factor of Tourism Development in the Regional University

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Abstract : An effective approach to the management of international educational mobility in regional universities with the purpose of increasing tourist activity in the region is considered.

Keywords : export and import of tourist and educational services, international academic mobility, regional tourist activities

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